

Understanding the Perception of IT Technicians in Adopting AI for Business Growth in Nepal

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is gradually becoming an essential part of business operations in different parts of the world. In Nepal as well, some businesses have started using AI for purposes such as online marketing, customer service, and managing business data. However, in districts like Chitwan and Nawalpur, where business activities are growing, there is still limited information about how IT professionals perceive the use of AI in business operations. Since IT technicians are at the heart of bringing new technologies into offices and companies, it's important to understand how they see these changes, what they experience in their daily work, and the challenges they face along the way.

This research has been conducted to check the awareness of IT technicians in regards to the application of AI in business, particularly in the districts of Nawalpur and Chitwan. It is also being done to see if AI can actually help in business growth. The study will use questionnaires and interviews with IT professionals from different companies and sectors. Through their answers, the research hopes to understand the problems they face, the opportunities they see, and what they suggest for making AI more useful for local businesses. The final goal is to help business owners, decision-makers, and technology providers plan better ways to bring AI into business in these districts.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, IT technicians, business growth, AI in Nepal, technology in business*